

SIMULATION MODEL OF REMOTE MONITORING SYSTEM BASED ON WIRELESS NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a simulation model of a remote monitoring system for agricultural land based on wireless network technologies was developed. The system is designed to monitor key parameters such as temperature, air humidity, soil moisture, and light in real time. Sensor nodes are connected to a central monitoring center via wireless communication technologies, and the data is processed on the server and compared with established standards. The monitoring center is modeled on the basis of Arduino MEGA and provides remote control via the Internet. The results of the study showed that there is a relationship between the monitored parameters, confirming the importance of the system for forecasting and effective management in agriculture.

I. Introduction:

Today, the rapid development of information and communication technologies allows for the widespread introduction of remote monitoring and control systems in various fields. In particular, monitoring systems based on wireless network technologies are gaining importance in industry, agriculture, ecology, healthcare, and the concept of "smart cities". These systems serve to increase the efficiency of processes by collecting, transmitting, and analyzing data in real time.

The main advantage of remote monitoring systems built on the basis of wireless sensor networks and IoT technologies is their flexibility, low energy consumption, and the ability to cover large areas. However, in the process of designing such systems, a thorough analysis of important factors such as network reliability, energy efficiency, data transmission delay, and interaction between nodes is required.

In this study, a simulation model of a remote monitoring system for agricultural land based on wireless network technologies is developed, and its main functional capabilities and performance are analyzed. The proposed model is of scientific and practical importance in the process of designing and optimizing monitoring systems and serves as an important methodological basis for creating real systems.

II. Wireless network technologies

Remote monitoring systems based on wireless network technologies play an important role in increasing the productivity of land areas in agriculture, rational use of resources, and ensuring safe and effective management. In this case, it is required to create a simulation model that allows for real-time analysis of the monitoring process, and this model is evaluated by parameters. At the same time, the main goal is to optimize the correspondence to real data and minimize the average relative error and is expressed as follows.

According to the concept put forward as a result of the research, the remote monitoring system of land areas has a simplified architecture consisting of three main stages Figure 1:

Figure-1: Structural diagram of the remote monitoring system for land areas

Data collection and transmission stage - at this stage, sensors are used to determine various parameters (temperature, humidity, light, soil moisture, etc.) placed on the ground. The sensors are combined in a cluster system and connected to a single transmission point through a control unit. Each sensor records the signal required for monitoring and sends it to the central server through the control unit. The process of collecting and transmitting digital signals from sensor nodes is carried out using GSM, 4G, 5G or Wi-Fi communication technologies.

Data processing and analysis stage - data from the sensors are collected on the central server, where their average values are determined. The values are compared with the established standards, and a normal or alarming state is determined. The control unit transmits these analyzes to the analysis center and ensures that a decision is made for each parameter. On the server, the signal data is automatically processed and re-analyzed based on the necessary algorithms.

Data presentation stage - processed monitoring data is presented to the user through a browser interface (web application), mobile application or other visual platforms. This allows users to analyze monitoring results in real time and make operational decisions.

Figure 2. Structural diagram of the monitoring center

The device designed for remote monitoring of land areas consists of a microcontroller control unit (Arduino MEGA), a wireless network module (ZigBee/Xbee), sensors (temperature, humidity, soil moisture, light), a local server and a visual interface. According to the scheme depicted in Figure 2, the physical parameters obtained from the sensors are converted into digital data using the Arduino MEGA microcontroller. This data is transmitted to the central monitoring server via wireless communication channels via the ZigBee module.

The monitoring center receives this data in real time and processes each parameter separately. The status is monitored using visual indicators (LEDs or graphic displays) based on the information received from the sensors. Through the interface of the central system, the user can:

- view temperature, humidity, light and other parameters;
- receive status analyses on the ecological or agrotechnical condition;
- take action based on warnings if necessary.

The central system also communicates with the server via the local network and through it connects to the Internet. This provides the operator or specialist with the opportunity for online monitoring, that is, it is possible to monitor the system status from anywhere, at any time.

Thus, the operator constantly has the latest and most accurate information about the status of all devices in the monitored area. The monitoring system monitors important parameters such as temperature, air humidity, soil moisture and light in the ground, taking into account the processes of collecting and processing measurement data based on a remote control device.

III. Simulation programs

Today, various simulator environments are used to model these processes, and a comparative analysis based on their technical and functional indicators is presented in Table 3.2, which allows us to determine in which cases and in what types of monitoring systems they can be effectively used (Table 1).

Table 1.

Functional comparison of simulation environments

Criteria	Simulation environment				
	Tinkercad	Multisim	MATLAB Simulink	LTspice	Proteus

Microcontroller modeling	Medium	Medium	Limited	No	High
Wireless communication modules	Limited	None	Extended (manual)	No	High (ZigBee, GSM)
Interactive visual interface	None	Limited	None	Low	Medium
User-friendliness	High	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Professional approach	Limited	High	High	High	High

From this analytical data, it can be concluded that the advantages of Proteus are that it is suitable for modeling complex wireless monitoring systems, it is possible to create a realistic model for GSM, ZigBee, GPS modules, and there is direct integration with programming (Arduino IDE, microcodes). At the same time, its interface is considered somewhat complicated for users, and its disadvantage is the fact that it is a licensed (paid) software.

The data acquisition layer in the model created in the Proteus environment is shown in Figure 4. Several sensors, a microcontroller (Arduino MEGA) and a wireless network module (for example, ZigBee or XBee) are placed at each field point. Together, these devices form a common network node. Through these nodes, real-time values of measurement parameters are collected and transmitted to the central node for high-level coordination. The central node, i.e. the coordinator, unlike conventional nodes, is additionally equipped with a GSM module.

Figure 4. Model for transmitting monitoring data from ground sites

The data collected by this module is sent to a remote server via the Internet. In this way, all elements of the system communicate wirelessly with each other, ensuring reliable data transmission to the central control and analysis center.

At the next stage, a monitoring center specially designed for monitoring and analyzing parameters received from the ground was modeled (Figure 5). The monitoring center is equipped with an Arduino MEGA microcontroller, a virtual terminal, a ZigBee/Xbee wireless

network module, an LCD display, as well as a GSM, Ethernet or Wi-Fi module that allows connecting to the Internet.

It is worth noting here that one of the main issues in the development of ground monitoring devices is their power supply. In order to effectively solve this problem, an additional solar panel module was added to the modeled circuit of the monitoring center to power it from solar energy.

The monitoring center receives the values of parameters received and transmitted from the ground, such as temperature, humidity, light and soil moisture, via the ZigBee/Xbee wireless network module. This information is displayed visually to the user in real time via a virtual terminal and LCD screen. At the same time, all parameters are transmitted to the web server via the Internet and stored in the server's memory.

Figure 5. Scheme of a monitoring center equipped with wireless network technologies

It is known that in the monitoring system there is a need to remotely monitor, control and evaluate the parameters of distributed systems. Based on this requirement, a separate web interface was created at the third stage of modeling using the capabilities of the Proteus environment (Figure 6). The web interface is accessed through any web browser, that is, by typing the server IP address in the address bar. As a result, the monitoring page shown in Figure 6 is created in the web browser. This web page is created on the basis of separate web windows for each land plot and allows you to display the values of important parameters (temperature, humidity, soil moisture, light) of agricultural land plots in real time in a graphical and numerical form.

Figure 6. Web interface of the land area monitoring model modeled in the Proteus environment

Through the web interface, the user will be able to visually monitor the changes in each parameter in real time. This makes it convenient to constantly monitor the system status, identify problems in a timely manner and eliminate them. As a result, it is also possible to evaluate, optimize and improve the system's performance. The system is highly reliable - the real-time transmission process has been shown to work with high accuracy in testing. The stability of the monitoring system has been proven, and the results observed under simulation conditions have proven that the system is able to provide accurate and reliable information even in a real environment.

Figure 7. Comparative analysis of transmitted and received values

Such graphical analyses are very important in assessing the fault tolerance, accuracy and stability of monitoring systems. Especially in areas such as agriculture, where external factors affect the system, a reliable monitoring system is of great importance in terms of productivity and resource conservation. This shows that the information is transmitted without any errors through the XBee network module.

In order to verify the efficiency and adequacy of the model, the monitoring results were analyzed for several key parameters. The observation dates of the land area were divided into randomly selected days. On each date, parameters such as temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), humidity (%), soil moisture (%) and light intensity (lux) were determined by the sensors and their change trends were observed. The monitoring results of these parameters are presented in table 2

table 2.

Proportional monitoring during the experimental-observation period of the monitoring model created in the Proteus software environment **natijalari**

No	Kuzatuv sanasi	Harorat ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Namlig (%)	Tuproq namlig (%)	Yorug'lik (lux)
1	20.03.2024	17.2	68	80	350
2	23.03.2024	17.8	68	80	375
3	30.03.2024	19.1	66.7	70	450
4	05.04.2024	21	63.2	71	450
5	24.04.2024	22,5	62.6	67	454
6	26.04.2024	23,4	61.7	67	461
7	01.05.2024	24,5	61,6	68	471

8	16.05.2024	26,9	60,8	65	492
9	28.05.2024	27,1	58,1	62	512
10	02.06.2024	28	57.8	60	600
11	14.06.2024	30.2	57.3	59	640
12	28.06.2024	32.3	56.8	57	658

The following graph, constructed based on statistical data from the monitoring system, clearly demonstrates the correlation of the results. The graph shows the trends in the change of key parameters such as temperature (°C), humidity (%), soil moisture (%), and light (lux) by observation date (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Correlation graph of results obtained from the monitoring simulation model

The results show that the temperature, humidity, and light parameters observed in the field are closely related to each other. In particular, a decrease in light intensity has a significant impact on the temperature and humidity of the ground. Changes in soil moisture and relative humidity in the air change in accordance with the temperature level. These results mean that the amount of light falling on the surface of the earth directly affects the temperature and humidity of the air. Also, the observed parameters, depending on each other, allow us to determine the impact of each change on the other indicator. This is of great importance in forecasting the monitoring system and planning agricultural activities.

Conclusion

The study developed a simulation model for remote monitoring of agricultural land based on wireless network technologies. The model allows real-time monitoring of key parameters such as temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and light. The results showed that there is a correlation between the parameters and that the system is compatible with real data and effective. The proposed solution will serve to improve monitoring and forecasting processes in agriculture..

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